

ST4TE

NEWSLETTER # 4

April 2026

Welcome to the ST4TE project!

We live in a world of transitions, with a shift We live in a world in and of transition. Across Europe and beyond, societies are moving toward greener models of production and consumption and adopting increasingly digital ways of working and living. These twin transitions promise long-term environmental benefits and fresh opportunities for sustainable economic growth. Yet a growing green and digital divide risks slowing progress and deepening inequalities between individuals, regions, and social groups, both today and in the years to come.

ST4TE (Strategies for Just and Equitable Transitions in Europe) is an EU-funded project dedicated to understanding these dynamics. It examines the drivers of the twin transition, the inequalities that emerge or intensify through it, and the policies needed to build greener, fairer, and more productive societies.

Over its three-year duration, ending in January 2027, ST4TE is carrying out research and outreach activities across Europe, engaging researchers, stakeholders, and policymakers with evidence-based insights.

ST4TE NEWS

Activities

Over the past months, ST4TE has entered a new and important phase of the project. Following extensive work in 2024–2025 on mapping policies, technologies, and the structural dimensions of the twin transition, efforts are now increasingly focused on dissemination, stakeholder engagement, and policy-oriented communication.

A growing share of project activity is now focusing on stakeholder engagement and co-creation, where partners are actively translating research insights into formats that are accessible and relevant for policymakers, stakeholders, and broader audiences. This includes:

- Strengthening engagement with policy and practice communities
- Developing communication materials tailored to different audiences
- Supporting dialogue around fairness and inclusion in the twin transition

This shift reflects the project's commitment not only to producing knowledge, but also to ensuring its findings contribute to ongoing

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debates and decision-making processes across Europe.

Co-creation Workshop in Gothenburg: From qualitative insights to practical action

The workshop in Gothenburg brought together a diverse group of participants from civil society, public institutions, and the private sector to engage with ST4TE research findings. The discussions centred on how the green and digital transition interacts with existing inequalities across Europe, and how these dynamics can be translated into more concrete and context-sensitive policy responses. Drawing on a broad analytical approach combining different types of data and perspectives, ST4TE research highlights how inequalities related to income, skills, health, gender, age, migration status, and place shape people's ability to participate in and benefit from ongoing transition processes, often reinforcing cycles of disadvantage.

The workshop unfolded largely as intended, with a strong emphasis on dialogue, reflection, and the joint development of policy-relevant ideas. Participants engaged actively with the factsheet materials, bringing in their own experiences and institutional perspectives to deepen the discussion and sharpen the relevance of the findings. A key outcome of the workshop was the synergy created by bringing together actors from different sectors and roles, enabling connections between lived realities, organisational practices, and policy frameworks. This exchange proved particularly valuable in moving from analysis to action. The combination of perspectives helped to identify both shared challenges and context-specific constraints, supporting the formulation of more grounded and

actionable recommendations tailored to different target groups, including civil society organisations, employers, and decision-makers at local and regional levels.

Overall, the contributions of external participants were central to the success of the workshop. Their engagement ensured that discussions moved beyond general insights and towards concrete implications, highlighting realistic pathways for more inclusive transition processes. The workshop thus marked an important step in operationalising research findings into policy-relevant knowledge, while also demonstrating the value of collaborative formats where research and practice can meaningfully inform one another.

Research results

Recent work has deepened the project's understanding of how the twin green and digital transition is experienced across different social groups and regions.

Emerging findings highlight that:

- The impacts of the twin transition are unevenly distributed, with significant variation across socio-economic groups, territories, and demographic categories.
- Inequalities are often intersectional and mutually reinforcing, rather than isolated or sector specific.
- Structural factors, such as access to infrastructure, skills, and institutional support, play a decisive role in shaping outcomes.

Importantly, the research underscores that achieving a successful twin transition requires attention not only to technological and environmental goals, but also to

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questions of fairness, inclusion, and social cohesion.

The health consequences of the Twin Transition

This report examines the health implications of the green, digital and twin transition across European regions. Using occupation-based measures of green, digital and hybrid (twin) jobs combined with SHARE and EHIS data, it analyses associations with both physical and mental health at the individual and regional level. Results show differentiated patterns: digital exposure is systematically linked to worse mental health and, for older cohorts, poorer physical health; green jobs are associated with poorer physical but more favourable mental health outcomes; twin-intensive environments tend to mitigate some adverse effects, particularly for mental health. Findings reveal marked educational and gender heterogeneity, highlighting potential intergenerational and territorial inequalities in the health consequences of structural transformation.

[Read the full report here](#)

Publications and presentations

Davidsson, A., Hultman, M., Strid, S., & Svenberg, S. (2026). *Caring as support of others' participation in the green, digital (and twin) transition* [Conference paper]. Sociology Days, 18-20 March, Linnaeus University, Sweden.

Dissemination of previous publications

Recent outputs have been used to engage audiences in discussions around: The social dimensions of the twin transition; Policy implications of emerging inequalities; The need for more inclusive and place-sensitive approaches.

These efforts mark an important step in ensuring that ST4TE contributes to evidence-informed policymaking and public debate across Europe. Overall, the project is now clearly transitioning from foundational analysis to impact-oriented communication and engagement, bringing research insights closer to the stakeholders and communities they are intended to support.

Meet the partners

Aristotle University

[Aristotle University of Thessaloniki](#) and its Urban and Regional Innovation Research Unit in Greece is the Project Coordinator. AUTH is responsible for tasks linking the project results to policymaking, e.g. the development of a twin transition index and the analysis of the territorial impact of the transitions.

EFIS Centre |

The [European Future Innovation System \(EFIS\) Centre](#) leads on the policy implications of the project, along with the sustainability, impact, and exploitation dimensions.

University of Ferrara

[The University of Ferrara](#) in Italy leads clarifying how European regions are affected by the green and digital transition and determining the influence of these factors on regional disparities.

Uni MERIT |

[UNU-MERIT](#) leads on estimating industry and occupation exposure to twin technologies, estimating the impact of inequality on the twin transition, and building a theoretical model to study the impacts on inequality of different energy and digital technology transitions scenarios.

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University of Gothenburg |

[UGOT's Department of Sociology and Work Science](#) in Sweden leads the task of narrative interviews in different European regions, the stakeholder engagement and validation of research results, and the research communication.

Gran Sasso Science Institute

[GSSI](#) in Italy will disentangle a series of effects that the green and digital transformations have on the work content, the health of individuals and the interconnectedness of territories in today's global markets.

CLIMAFIN |

[CLIMAFIN](#) in France contributes to mapping and measuring financial risks and opportunities associated with the twin transitions.

Utrecht University |

[Utrecht University's](#) Economic Geography Team in the Netherlands is mapping the pathways toward Europe's green and digital transformation to investigate the strengths and challenges encountered by European regions in developing green, digital, and twin technologies.

Sister projects

MOBI-TWIN: Twin Transition and changing patterns of spatial mobility: a regional approach MOBI-TWIN aims to comprehend the intricate patterns of mobility and leverage this knowledge to foster regional prosperity. Website: <https://mobi-twin-project.eu/>

FITTER-EU: Fair and Inclusive Twin Transitions for a Stronger Social Europe. FITTER-EU is aimed at contributing to existing research on the origins, dynamics

and determinants of inequalities and enable anticipatory governance to support a fair and inclusive twin transition in Europe.

Website: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/fitter-eu>

READJUST: Just Transition to a Green and Digital Future for all. READJUST strives to address the inequalities created or exacerbated by the twin transitions policies and it aims to suggest policy options for overcoming the potential trade-offs between efficiency and equality in twin transitions in the key sectors of mobility and agri-food.

Website: <https://readjust.eu/>

About the ST4TE project

The importance of the green and digital transitions is evident in addressing the impacts of climate change. As a result, there is a growing need for more data to assess the potential perpetuation or exacerbation of inequalities. Various sectors undergoing the twin transitions (TT) are currently experiencing disparities that could persist, or worsen, during this transformative period. Therefore, the EU-funded ST4TE project has been designed to comprehend the impact of the twin transitions on green goals and vulnerable European regions. The project will also study the forces behind these transitions, understand potential inequalities and their causes, and collaborate with policymakers. The final objective is to ensure that the green and digital transitions contribute to a more equitable and sustainable future.

Click [here](#) to find out more about ST4TE.

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